

A stainless steel metal cart with a curved top and wheels. The cart has a rectangular base with a flat bottom and a curved top structure supported by vertical posts. It has four wheels, with the front two being casters and the back two being larger wheels. The cart is shown from a side perspective, angled towards the right. The background is white with a yellow geometric shape on the left side.

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